

Fundamental Study on the Control of Biological Nitrous Oxide Production Using Nitric Oxide as the Indicator in Wastewater Treatment Process

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Abstract

In this study, we examined methods to control nitrous oxide (N_2O), a potent greenhouse gas produced by microorganisms in the process of biological wastewater treatment. Nitric oxide (NO) has been shown to be an effective indicator for controlling N_2O production by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), and this study aims to extend the scope of basic theory that contributes to the establishment of technology for controlling N_2O production in wastewater treatment plants, using NO as the engineering indicator, to complex microbial systems that include not only AOB but also denitrifying bacteria and others. The activated sludge collected from wastewater treatment plants was tested, and it was confirmed that NO was the dominant factor in the conversion rate and production rate of N_2O in both anaerobic, aerobic and anoxic tanks.

Keywords

Global warming; nitric oxide; nitrous oxide; nitrifier denitrification; wastewater treatment plant

INTRODUCTION

Research background

Nitrous oxide (N_2O), which has a greenhouse effect 273 times greater than that of carbon dioxide, is commonly produced in biological wastewater treatment processes. Ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), nitrite-oxidizing bacteria, and denitrifying bacteria are known to produce N_2O . However, N_2O production by AOB under nitrification conditions is the major source of N_2O production in the wastewater treatment process. Previous findings have shown that increasing nitrite concentration and decreasing dissolved oxygen (DO) affect N_2O production by AOB but there are many factors not yet clarified, such as the details of the metabolic mechanism, and control methods for N_2O production have not yet been established.

N_2O production by nitrifying bacteria and precursor NO

The hydroxylamine pathway and the nitrite denitrification pathway have been reported as the pathways for N_2O production by AOB, but the precursor of N_2O in both pathways is nitric oxide (NO). It has been experimentally confirmed that AOB utilizes dinitrogen tetroxide (N_2O_4), which is produced by the chemical reaction of NO with oxygen, as an electron acceptor in ammonia oxidation, and that the depletion of N_2O_4 inhibits ammonia oxidation even under aerobic conditions[1]. Therefore, it is considered that AOB produces NO to provide electron acceptors necessary to obtain energy for ammonia oxidation but also reduces excess NO to N_2O as a defense against NO toxicity (Figure-1). According to previous reports, the artificial supply or removal of NO to AOB affects the activity of ammonia oxidation [2].

Nevertheless, if NO is to contribute to N_2O emission control in actual wastewater treatment plants, it is necessary to verify the effectiveness of NO as a control indicator in more complex microbial systems including denitrifying bacteria. Thus, in this study, we experimentally verified the basic theory that contributes to the establishment of N_2O production control technology using NO as a

control index, using activated sludge from actual wastewater treatment plants in order to extend the theory to complex microbial systems including nitrite-oxidizing bacteria and denitrifying bacteria, which are considered to be affected by NO in addition to AOB. Specifically, this study focused on changes in DO and hydraulic mixing of activated sludge under different environmental conditions to confirm that the amount of NO is the dominant factor in N₂O production even when activated sludge is subjected to changes in environmental conditions. In addition, we developed the on-site test method to immediately measure the production and resolution of NO and N₂O by activated sludge in actual wastewater treatment plants, and demonstrated the applicability of the method in the wastewater treatment plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Development of on-site syringe testing methods

In order to evaluate NO and N₂O production from activated sludge in wastewater treatment processes, it is necessary to accurately measure the concentration of dissolved gases in sludge samples, which requires vapor-liquid equilibrium operation in a closed container or the use of a dissolved gas sensor. In addition, for determining NO and N₂O production and decomposition under various environmental conditions, there is a need to set various environmental conditions for the same sludge, but the simultaneous setting of these conditions is often limited in laboratory-scale reaction tanks. Therefore, we developed a simple evaluation method using plastic syringes (Figure-2). In wastewater treatment plants, activated sludge mixture is collected from a reaction tank using a water sampler, and 20 mL of sludge is quickly aspirated using a syringe with an effective volume of 100 mL. After attaching the needle to the syringe, aspirate 80 mL of the concentration control gas previously filled in aluminum bags for various test purposes, seal the syringe with stopcock, and allow a predetermined biological reaction time on the shaker. After the reaction, the gas phase in the syringe is collected into aluminum bags with effective volume of 100 mL and analyzed for various gas concentrations. The liquid phase is filtered through a syringe filter and provided for analysis of inorganic nitrogen concentration. This method makes it possible to set various environmental conditions for activated sludge simultaneously and is easy to operate in actual wastewater treatment plants because it is a simple method using a plastic syringe.

N₂O and NO production rate test

Since it is generally known that DO affects the metabolism of both nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria, N₂O and NO production rate tests were conducted to verify the interrelationship between NO and N₂O production in activated sludge under different oxygen concentrations. The oxygen concentrations in the gas phase were 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.0% in the syringe test method described previously, and the biological reaction time was 1 hour.

Activated sludge mixing test

To confirm that NO is the dominant factor in N₂O production even in activated sludge mixtures with different N₂O and NO production and decomposition potentials, the sludge mixing test was conducted using the syringe test method described previously. Activated sludge collected from anaerobic and upstream aerobic tanks was mixed in a syringe to five mixing ratios (by volume) of 1:0, 3:1, 1:1, 1:3, and 0:1, to observe NO and N₂O production characteristics. Gas-phase oxygen concentrations were set at 0.5% and 1.7%, and the reaction time was 1 hour.

Target wastewater treatment plants for this study

In this study, activated sludge samples were collected and tested in the full-scale wastewater treatment plant operating in Japan. The treatment process of the wastewater treatment plant consists of the

anaerobic tank, upstream aerobic tank, anoxic tank, and downstream aerobic tank in order from the inflow side, and the activated sludge in the adjacent tanks can be mixed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

N₂O and NO production rate test

Figure-3 shows that N₂O conversion rate tends to increase with increasing oxygen concentration in anaerobic, upstream aerobic, and anoxic tanks. The N₂O production and conversion rate at 0.5% and 1.0% oxygen were relatively low, and a negative conversion rate, i.e., N₂O decomposition, was observed in the anaerobic and anoxic tanks. Oxygen concentrations of 0.5% and 1.0% were approximately 0.2-0.4 mg L⁻¹ DO equivalent, suggesting that the reduction of N₂O by denitrifying bacteria was predominant for N₂O production under conditions of limited oxygen supply. The downstream aerobic tank showed specific results, with N₂O reduction observed under all oxygen concentrations.

Next, Figure-4, which shows the total amount of NO in the syringe at the initial and end of the reaction, indicates that the relationship between the amount of NO at each sampling point and the oxygen concentration is generally consistent with the N₂O conversion rate. On the other hand, the excellence of decomposition as observed for N₂O is not observed for NO, and the amount of NO change corresponding to data with a negative N₂O conversion rate is observed as a relatively low production of positive values. Based on the hypothesis that AOB reduces NO to avoid biotoxicity and that denitrifying bacteria have a mechanism to mitigate NO-induced metabolic inhibition, it can be inferred that N₂O production is suppressed in the downstream aerobic tank as a result of maintaining a NO concentration range that does not require NO reduction to N₂O for both bacteria. Therefore, the possibility was demonstrated that N₂O production by AOB and denitrifying bacteria could be controlled by optimizing NO concentrations. In fact, the relationship between the N₂O conversion rate and total NO amount for the aforementioned experimental data shows a strong positive correlation, meaning that the amount of NO production dominates the conversion rate of ammonia nitrogen to N₂O (Figure-5).

Activated sludge mixing test

Figure-6 shows the concentrations of NO and N₂O in the gas phase at the initial and end of the reaction in the syringe test using mixed activated sludge collected from the aerobic tank upstream and anaerobic tank. For 0.5% oxygen concentration (Figure-6 (a)), it can be seen that the amount of NO and N₂O production increases with the mixing ratio of the anaerobic tank sludge. Therefore, under 0.5% oxygen conditions, the NO and N₂O production potential of the anaerobic tank sludge is relatively high. On the other hand, for 1.7% oxygen (Figure-6 (b)), the overall trend is in contrast to that for 0.5% oxygen, with NO and N₂O production increasing with the mixing ratio of aerobic tank sludge. These results suggest that the characteristic of activated sludge to produce and decompose NO and N₂O under given dissolved oxygen concentration conditions varies significantly depending on the environmental conditions to which the activated sludge was exposed immediately before.

In order to verify whether NO can be used as the control indicator of N₂O production even in a mixture of activated sludge with different NO and N₂O production and decomposition characteristics as described above, we calculated the total NO and N₂O production rate in each syringe at the end of the reaction and visualized the relationship between them. The results shown in Figure-7 indicate that the relationship between the total amount of NO and the N₂O production rate is strongly correlated, i.e., the NO concentration is the rate-limiting factor for N₂O production, regardless of the differences in NO and N₂O production characteristics, DO, or mixing ratio of the activated sludge. Using NO as

a monitoring indicator in wastewater treatment plants will make it possible to estimate and control changes in N₂O production even in complex microbial systems in which not only nitrifying bacteria but also denitrifying bacteria coexist.

Figure-1 NO utilization and N₂O production by AOB

Figure-3 Initial oxygen concentration and N₂O conversion rate

Figure-5 Total amount of NO and N₂O conversion rate

Figure-2 On-site test method for NO and N₂O production

Figure-4 Initial oxygen concentration and NO concentration

Figure-7 NO concentration and N₂O production rate

Figure-6 Effect of initial oxygen concentration and sludge mixing ratio on NO and N₂O production

References

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